

Novafert

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D4.2 – NOVAFERT demo network

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<i>Version:</i>	<i>Final Version</i>
<i>Quality review:</i>	<i>Ana Robles, UVIC</i> <i>Morana jednacak, IPS-KONZALTING</i>
<i>Date:</i>	<i>31/08/2025</i>
<i>Dissemination level:</i>	<i>Public (PU)</i>
<i>Grant Agreement N°:</i>	<i>101060835</i>
<i>Starting Date:</i>	<i>01-09-2022</i>
<i>Duration:</i>	<i>36 months</i>
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1. Introduction

The main objective of NOVAFERT is to demonstrate the technical, economic and environmental feasibility of a wide range of alternative fertilising products containing recovered nutrients from different waste streams. The goal is to replace reliance on synthetic and mineral fertilisers, thus reducing environmental impacts and external nutrient dependence in agriculture in representative countries from Eastern, Western, Northern, Southern and Central Europe. As part of the NOVAFERT project, the aim is to improve agricultural knowledge exchange regarding the use of alternative fertilisers in EU member states. Following on from the mapping exercise of nutrient recovery technologies and derived products and the development of a nutrient-oriented living lab atlas in WP1, seven lighthouse demonstrations were established (1 per region) for WP4. The purpose of lighthouse demonstrations is to act as a front runner for nutrient use within an area and act as a support hub for the knowledge exchange in a supportive environment, facilitated by each project partner.

In order to expedite market uptake of sustainable innovations, end users such as farmers need to observe at relevant/practical scale how novel products perform from an agronomic and environmental perspective and how they can be incorporated into nutrient management planning. The supportive environment will act as a hub where farmers themselves can educate their peers and inspire the use of alternative fertilisers after completion of the Novafert project.

The following report is focused on documenting the facilitation of knowledge exchange to groups of farmers at each of the lighthouse demonstrations in each region, with a target of 35 events (5 per region). The report will proceed region by region, providing a description of each lighthouse followed by an account of the events conducted there, and will include, where applicable, a justification for any instances in which a lighthouse has not achieved the targeted number of visits. Due to practicalities and logistics in some regions it was not feasible to host all required events at the lighthouse demonstration site. However relevant information on the lighthouse demonstration was still disseminated to participants at the given events, making it applicable. Therefore, the lighthouse demonstrations also served as an important advocate for consumers throughout Europe by providing information and showcasing that farmers are engaging in alternative strategies to reduce their dependence on chemical fertiliser for food production.

2. Lighthouse demonstration – Ireland

Teagasc established a grassland sister trial to an arable trial and is in its 5th year. The purpose of the demonstration trial is to assess the agronomic benefits of different bio-based recycled-derived fertilisers at a field-scale level. The primary goal is to determine how these fertilisers can enhance soil fertility by increasing carbon and major nutrient levels in the soil. Progress is being monitored by analysing crop yield and quality.

The aim of this lighthouse demonstration is to promote nutrient recovery and recycling from different agri-food processing waste resources. Additionally, the focus is on helping farmers understand and adopt these bio-based recycled fertilisers as options for their own grassland and arable systems.

The grassland trial site is used within the Irish Novafert lighthouse demonstration to test the efficacy of several parameters, such as grass yield, soil fertility, soil organic matter, and soil biology indicators. Products are also demonstrated at large-scale applications on the Teagasc beef and dairy farm in Teagasc Johnstown Castle and demonstration tillage farms. Large-scale demonstration is used as part of the Lighthouse demonstration to test the practicalities, such as fertiliser spreader calibration for applying different types of products with standard machinery that is already available on Irish farms. Through this type of demonstration, we can assess their efficacy in a controlled environment and identify any potential challenges that may arise when used on a large scale. This type of information is disseminated to farmers as a support tool that is interested in adapting the use of these novel fertilisers on their own farms. There was a total of 8 lighthouse demonstration visits in Ireland as the nature of the site was prepared for visits and demonstrations making it feasible and more practical compared to some of the other lighthouse demonstrations. This helped us reach the target of 35 lighthouse demonstration events in total making up for a shortfall of two in the Catalonian region and one in Flanders as they were unable to fulfill the required five.

Figure 1. Teagasc long-term lighthouse demonstration trial

Figure 2. Live demonstration of cattle slurry separation

Figure 3. Large scale application of pelletised poultry manure

Figure 4. Large scale application of cattle slurry using

2.1 Type of fertiliser/s being tested and demonstrated

The grassland trial consists of a perennial ryegrass sward. The trial consists of ten fertiliser treatments with five replicates of each, along with three zero fertiliser plots. The nine fertiliser treatments consist of mainstream fertiliser and eight alternative sources of fertiliser, including:

- Cattle slurry
- Pig and cattle slurry solids
- Aluminum precipitated dairy processing sludge
- Calcium precipitated dairy processing sludge
- Struvite from potato processing wastewater
- Struvite from municipal wastewater
- Incinerated poultry litter
- Incinerated sewage sludge
- Poultry manure pellets
- Meat and bone meal

The alternative sources of fertiliser did not provide all the crops' N, P, K and S requirements. Treatments were balanced with chemical fertiliser to ensure all plots received the same amount of nutrients for optimal yield. **Fout! Verwijzingsbron niet gevonden.** below outlines the chemical composition of the alternative fertilisers used within the lighthouse demonstration field-scale grassland site.

Table 1. Chemical composition of the alternative fertiliser used in a nutrient management plan

Bio-based fertiliser	Sample	Chemical composition	Source/Feedstock
Cattle slurry		0.6%P, 4.3%K, 0.4%S (dry basis)	Livestock animals
CT Struvite		MgPO ₄ NH ₄ .6H ₂ O (10.7%P, 5.1%N, 9.9% Mg, 1.2%K)	Potato processing wastewater
VEV Struvite		MgPO ₄ NH ₄ .6H ₂ O (10%P, 5.1%N, 9.4% Mg, 0.06%K)	Sewage sludge
Outotec Ash		CaNaPO ₄ (8.4%P, 10%Na, 10.3% Ca) (dry basis)	Incineration or gasification of sewage sludge
BMC Ash		5.5%P, 10.7%K, 3% S, 15.6%Ca, 3.5%Mg (dry basis)	Incineration of poultry litter in biomass power
Lime dairy sludge		4.6%P, 6%N, 3%Ca, 3%Al, 1.6%K, 0.6%S (dry basis)	Dairy food processing wastewater
Activated sludge		8.1%P, 1.8%N, 24%Ca, 0.4%K, 0.3% S (dry basis)	Dairy food processing wastewater

2.1.1 Application strategies for fertiliser

The composition and texture of alternative fertiliser can vary, mainly due to the range of dry matter content from low to high. Therefore, spreading these types of products with precision on a large scale on farms can become a challenge for farmers and act as a barrier for adaptation. One of the focuses of the Novafert LH demos is to gain and provide a greater insight into the application of products that are in use in the field and to note any difficulties or challenges that need to be addressed to provide better advice to farmers if interested in using different types of alternative fertiliser. Since cattle slurry is the most available alternative nutrient source to chemical fertiliser on Irish farms, a lot of attention is placed on the correct management of this source to gain the best possible return. Similar application advice applies to all other low DM slurries for land application to minimize losses to the environment. Figure 5 is an outline of best practice when applying slurry.

Figure 5. Application strategies for slurry (W.Burchill,2018)

2.1.2 Cost analysis and mineral fertiliser replacement value for alternative fertiliser/s

Below is the cost analysis based on yield, and P & K inputs for a crop of spring organic oats using several types of alternative fertilisers that are also included in the grassland trial in the lighthouse demonstration. This spring organic oat trial was selected as a nutrient-oriented living lab and is important to gain information on how these types of fertilisers can be adapted in other crops. Figures below (Table 2) are based on the return of the straw to the soil.

Table 2. Cost analysis for alternative fertilisers used in a spring organic oat crop

Treatment	Extra Yield	Cost	P Gain/Loss	K Gain/Loss	Net Gain/Loss
Untreated	0	0	- €60/ha	- €42/ha	- €102/ha
PM Pellets 0.5t	€246	€272	- €16/ha	+ €14/ha	- €28/ha
Cattle Slurry	€299	€125	+ €5/ha	+ €176/ha	+ €355/ha
Dairy Sludge	€86	0	+ €9/ha	- €32/ha	+ €63/ha

1st cut grass silage

Below (

) are mineral fertiliser replacement values for including several different types of fertilisers into a fertiliser programme for grass silage. Calculations above based on N €1.27kg, 16% P €3.52kg, 50% K €1.18kg, S €0.73kg

Table 3. Cost analysis for alternative fertilisers used for a first cut of silage

Bio-based fertiliser	t/ha	% of mineral fertiliser displaced (Index 2 soil 1 st cut silage)				Value €/ha
		N	P	K	S	
Lime dairy sludge	1.7	4	100	1	4	114
Activated sludge	6.8	32	100	3	25	164
Cattle slurry	33	48	55	56	38	242
Potato struvite	0.3	12	100	2	0	128
Sewage struvite	0.3	12	100	0	0	125
Ash poultry	0.6	0	100	37	83	186
Ash sewage	0.4	0	100	3	53	119
Lime dairy sludge	1.7	4	100	1	4	114
Activated sludge	6.8	32	100	3	25	164
Cattle slurry	33	48	55	56	38	242
Potato struvite	0.3	12	100	2	0	128
Sewage struvite	0.3	12	100	0	0	125
Ash poultry	0.6	0	100	37	83	186
Ash sewage	0.4	0	100	3	53	119

2.2 Details and evidence of the five farmer group visits to the lighthouse demonstration site

2.2.1 Group visit 1

General information

Region: Ireland

Date of Visit: 16/03/2023

Number of farm attendees: 100 +

Relevant information/material used

- An introduction to the main objectives of the Novafert project was provided
- Sample fertiliser products were placed on display for attendees to have a look at the texture of a range of alternative fertilisers being used in the field
- Nutrient analysis and the origin of each fertiliser were available for farmers
- An information board was used to provide information to the farmers regarding to the cost of using these products at farm scale, application strategies for different types of alternative fertilisers and the mineral fertiliser replacement value for a range of alternative fertilisers being used on farm (Information displayed to farmers is provided within 2.1.1 -2.1.3 above)

Pictures of event

Group gathered around information board

Sample fertilisers used as props for attendees

2.2.2 Group visit 2

General information

Region:	Ireland
Date of Visit:	16/11/2023
Number of farmer attendees:	35

Relevant information/material used

- An introduction to the main objectives of the Novafert project was provided
- Sample fertiliser products were placed on display for attendees to have a look at the texture of a range of alternative fertiliser being used in the field
- Nutrient analysis and the origin of each fertiliser were available for farmers
- A PowerPoint presentation was used to provide information to the farmers regarding the cost of using these products at farm scale, application strategies for different types of alternative fertilisers and the mineral fertiliser replacement value for a range of alternative fertilisers being used on farm (Information displayed to farmers is provided within 2.1.1 -2.1.3 above)

Pictures of event

Group gathered inside for dissemination of information

2.2.3 Group visit 3

General information

Region:	Ireland
Date of Visit:	16/07/2024
Number of farmer attendees:	1000+

Relevant information/material used

- An introduction to the main objectives of the Novafert project was provided
- Sample fertiliser products were placed on display for attendees to have a look at the texture of a range of alternative fertilisers being used in the field
- Nutrient analysis and origin of each fertiliser were available for farmers
- A board presentation was used to provide information to the farmers regarding the cost of using these products at farm scale, application strategies for different types of alternative fertilisers and the mineral fertiliser replacement value for a range of alternative fertilisers being used on farm (Information displayed to farmers is provided within 2.1.1 -2.1.3 above)

Pictures of event

Live demonstration of cattle slurry separation

Farmers visiting the alternative fertiliser stand

2.2.4 Group visit 4

General information

Region:	Ireland
Date of Visit:	25/07/2024
Number of farmer attendees:	40

- An introduction to the main objectives of the Novafert project was provided
- Sample fertiliser products were placed on display for attendees to have a look at the texture of a range of alternative fertilisers being used in the field
- Nutrient analysis and the origin of each fertiliser were available for farmers
- A PowerPoint presentation was used to provide information to the farmers regarding the cost of using these products at farm scale, application strategies for different types of alternative fertilisers and the mineral fertiliser replacement value for a range of alternative fertilisers being used on farm (Information displayed to farmers is provided within 2.1.1 -2.1.3 above)

Relevant information/material used

Pictures of event

Farmers receiving information on fertiliser

Farmers visiting in field use of fertiliser

2.2.5 Group visit 5

General information

Region:	Ireland
Date of Visit:	14/11/2024
Number of farmer attendees:	25

Relevant information/material used

- An introduction to the main objectives of the Novafert project was provided
- Sample fertiliser products were placed on display for attendees to have a look at the texture of a range of alternative fertilisers being used in the field
- Nutrient analysis and the origin of each fertiliser were available for farmers
- A PowerPoint presentation was used to provide information to the farmers regarding the cost of using these products at farm scale, application strategies for different types of alternative fertilisers and the mineral fertiliser replacement value for a range of alternative fertilisers being used on farm (Information displayed to farmers is provided within 2.1.1 - 2.1.3 above)

Pictures of event

Farmers visiting grassland trial where a range of alternative fertilisers are being used

2.2.6 Group visit 6

General information

Region:	Ireland
Date of Visit:	23/06/2025
Number of farmer attendees:	30

Relevant information/material used

- An introduction of the main objectives to the Novafert project was provided
- Sample fertiliser products were placed on display for attendees to have a look at the texture of a range of alternative fertiliser being used in the field
- Nutrient analysis and origin of each fertiliser was available for farmers
- A power point presentation was used to provide information to the farmers regarding the cost of using these products at farm scale in an organic oat crop, application strategies for different types of alternative fertilisers and the mineral fertiliser replacement value for a range of alternative fertilisers being used on farms (Information displayed to farmers is provided within 2.1.1 -2.1.3 above)

Pictures of event

Farmers visiting a field of organic oats after receiving different fertiliser treatments

2.2.7 Group visit 7

General information

Region:	Ireland
Date of Visit:	25/06/2025
Number of farmer attendees:	2,000 +

Relevant information/material used

- An introduction of the main objectives to the Novafert project was provided
- Sample fertiliser products were placed on display for attendees to have a look at the texture of a range of alternative fertiliser being used in the field
- Nutrient analysis and origin of each fertiliser was available for farmers
- A billboard presentation was used to provide information to the farmers regarding the cost of using these products at farm scale over a six year tillage rotation, application strategies for different types of alternative fertilisers and the mineral fertiliser replacement value for a range of alternative fertilisers being used on farm (Information displayed to farmers is provided within 2.1.1 -2.1.3 above)

Pictures of event

Farmers visiting the lighthouse demonstration for practical insights on fertiliser type for an arable rotation

2.2.8 Group visit 8

General information

Region:	Ireland
Date of Visit:	15/07/2025
Number of farmer attendees:	40

Relevant information/material used

- An introduction of the main objectives to the Novafert project was provided
- Sample fertiliser products were placed on display for attendees to have a look at the texture of a range of alternative fertiliser being used in the field
- Nutrient analysis and origin of each fertiliser was available for farmers
- A power point presentation was used to provide information to the farmers regarding the cost of using these products at farm scale in a grassland silage crop, application strategies for different types of alternative fertilisers and the mineral fertiliser replacement value for a range of alternative fertilisers being used on farms (Information displayed to farmers is provided within 2.1.1 -2.1.3 above)

Pictures of event

Farmers visiting the lighthouse demonstration site

3. Lighthouse demonstration – Poland

The Municipal Water and Sewerage Company in Rzeszów, Poland, is responsible for managing wastewater treatment within the urban agglomeration of the city and surrounding areas. Annually, the company processes approximately 17 million cubic meters of wastewater, which results in the generation of about 20,000 tons of sewage sludge as a byproduct of the treatment process. To manage this waste in an environmentally sustainable manner, the Municipal Water and Sewerage Company utilizes drying technology to treat around 5,000 tons of this sludge, significantly reducing its volume and preparing it for further use.

One of the key innovations introduced by the company is the production of an organic soil improver – Glebex +. This product is made from dried sewage sludge and serves as an eco-friendly alternative to synthetic fertilisers. It contains valuable organic matter and nutrients beneficial for soil regeneration and plant growth.

The first batches of Glebex+ were produced in spring 2022, marking the beginning of a new direction in Municipal Water and Sewerage Company's approach to circular economy and waste valorisation. In its inaugural year, the company produced 1,400 tons of Glebex+, all of which were successfully sold, indicating a strong market interest and demand for the product. This enthusiastic reception demonstrated the potential of Glebex+ as a viable product in the agricultural and gardening sectors.

Encouraged by this success, Municipal Water and Sewerage Company plans to continue production at a similar level in the coming years, with the flexibility to scale up output depending on market conditions and demand. The company is monitoring the evolving needs of both large-scale agricultural producers and individual gardeners, aiming to provide a consistent supply of the product while promoting sustainable farming practices.

The growing popularity of Glebex+ is closely tied to the rising costs of conventional chemical fertilisers, which have led many farmers and home growers to seek more affordable and environmentally responsible alternatives. Glebex+ offers not only a cost-effective solution but also contributes to soil health improvement, supporting the long-term fertility of agricultural land.

In addition to economic and environmental benefits, the use of Glebex+ aligns with broader EU and national policies promoting circular economy principles and the reduction of landfill waste. By turning sewage sludge into a marketable product, the company is setting a positive example of innovation and sustainability in municipal services.

Figure 6. Municipal Water and Sewerage Company in Rzeszów

3.1 Type of fertiliser/s being tested and demonstrated

Glebex+ is a soil improver from sewage sludge produced in the Municipal Water and Sewerage Company in Rzeszów. Dehydrated and dried sewage sludge is processed into a fertiliser. In the municipal sewage treatment plant, approximately 20,000 tons of sewage sludge are generated. Out of this amount, about 5,000 tons of sludge are dried. From these, approximately 1,000 tons of organic soil improver are produced.

Glebex+ is produced from stabilized municipal sewage sludge dried at a temperature of 130°C. It is enriched with microbiological preparations.

Table 4. Chemical composition of soil improver - Glebex+

Product	Sample	Chemical composition	Source
Glebex+		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 38 kg of N, • 39 kg of P, • 5 kg of K, • >50% organic matter (d.m.) 	Sewage sludge

3.1.1 Application strategies of fertiliser

Scope of application

Glebex+ can be used in a variety of agricultural and horticultural settings, including:

- in field cultivation of agricultural crops,

- on grasslands (meadows),
- in ornamental plant cultivation and gardens,
- on lawns, eg, during establishment or regeneration,
- for the reclamation of degraded land and for improving soils low in organic matter.

Due to its natural origin and the absence of chemical additives, Glebex+ can be safely used in home and allotment gardens. This makes the product an environmentally friendly alternative to synthetic fertilisers, particularly in situations where the focus is not only on crop yields, but also on environmental protection and long-term soil health.

Recommended application rates

- **Field crops:** up to 3.5 t/ha,
- **Reclamation of degraded land:** up to 3.0 t/ha,
- **Grasslands:** 1.5 – 3.5 t/ha (depending on the phosphorus content in the soil),
- **Ornamental plants and lawns:** up to 3.5 t/ha (approximately 3.5 kg per 10 m²).

3.1.2 Cost analysis and mineral fertiliser replacement value for alternative fertiliser/s

Cost analysis

The production cost of alternative products like Glebex+ is typically lower than that of synthetic mineral fertilisers, primarily because:

- They are based on by-products of municipal wastewater treatment (e.g., sewage sludge), which reduces raw material costs,
- Thermal drying and granulation are relatively energy-intensive but are offset by lower input costs and the use of existing infrastructure (e.g., WWTPs),
- The market price of Glebex+ is generally lower than that of mineral fertilisers, often in the range of 200–300 PLN per tonne (273 PLN in 2023).

Compared to mineral fertilisers (e.g. NPK blends), which may cost 2,500– 4000 PLN per tonne or more, Glebex+ offers substantial savings per hectare, especially for large-scale applications or land reclamation projects

Nutrient replacement value

Based on its composition, Glebex+ contains approximately:

- 3.8% N – 38 kg/t,
- 3.9% P as P₂O₅ - 39 kg/t,
- 5.0% K as K₂O - 50 kg/t.

To illustrate this, **Fout! Verwijzingsbron niet gevonden.** compares the nutrient content of 1 tonne of Glebex+ with the average market value of equivalent mineral fertiliser components.

Table 5. Macronutrient content and equivalent value of Glebex+ relative to NPK fertilisers

Nutrient	Quantity in Glebex+ (kg/t)	Market value (PLN)*
Nitrogen (N)	38 kg	~180 PLN
Phosphorus (P)	39 kg	~150 PLN
Potassium (K)	50 kg	~160 PLN
Total value	-	~ 490 PLN

* Based on average 2023 fertiliser prices in Poland.

This indicates that the replacement value of Glebex+ is often higher than its selling price, making it a cost-effective fertiliser substitute.

In addition to direct cost savings, Glebex+ provides long-term agronomic benefits that are not priced in the fertiliser market, including:

- increased soil organic matter and improved structure,
- enhanced water retention capacity,
- stimulated biological activity,
- contribution to circular economy goals and local nutrient recycling.

Overall, Glebex+ represents not only a cost-efficient fertiliser replacement, but also a sustainable soil management solution.

3.2 Details and evidence of the five farmer group visits to the lighthouse demonstration site

3.2.1 Group visit 1

General information

Region:	Poland
Date of Visit:	27.08.2024
Number of farmer attendees:	16

Relevant information/material used

Introduction to the NOVAFERT project:

- Presentation by Prof. Marzena Smol (MEERI PAS).
- Overview of the project's main objectives related to developing sustainable fertiliser solutions in line with EU environmental policies.

Presentation of research findings:

- Delivered by Paulina Marcinek (MEERI PAS).
- Results from the Atlas of Nutrient-Oriented Living Labs.
- Emphasis on the role of innovative fertilisers, such as Glebex+, in fostering a circular economy and their potential for international recognition.

Presentation and site visit to the production facility:

- Led by Bartosz Wadiak (Municipal Water and Sewage Company).
- Demonstration of the Glebex+ production process and its potential applications in sustainable agriculture.

Discussion and exchange of experiences:

- Active participation from attendees, particularly farmers.
- Exploration of the practical aspects of using fertilisers derived from secondary raw materials.

Evaluation survey:

- Conducted as part of the NOVAFERT project.
- Collection of feedback and suggestions for future project development.

Significance of alternative fertilisers:

- Highlighting the role of innovative fertilisers in addressing environmental challenges.
- Supporting the advancement of sustainable agricultural practices.

Event Promotion:

- Invitations sent via email to agricultural advisors.
- Information shared through social media channels of the Division of Biogenic Raw Materials at MEERI PAS (Facebook, LinkedIn, X).

Pictures of event

The tour of the Municipal Water
and Sewerage Company

The tour of the Glebex+ production facility

3.2.2 Group visit 2

General information

Region:	Poland
Date of Visit:	12.03.2025
Number of farmer attendees:	15

Relevant information/material used

As part of the 2nd NOVAFERT study visit on 12th March 2025, a group of farmers with hands-on experience in nutrient management on small and medium-sized farms took part in a dedicated session. The meeting aimed to better understand the practical needs, challenges, and perspectives of agricultural practitioners regarding the use of alternative fertilisers derived from secondary raw materials.

The session began with a short introduction to the NOVAFERT project, its goals, and the relevance of promoting circular approaches in fertiliser production. The farmers expressed strong interest in learning more about new fertilising solutions, particularly those aligned with sustainable and locally available sources.

Key aspects of the session included:

- an open discussion on current fertilisation practices used by small and medium-sized farms, with a focus on the benefits and limitations of animal manure,
- an overview of alternative fertilisers analysed within the NOVAFERT project,
- The introduction of Glebex+ as a case example of an innovative product, derived from thermally dried sewage sludge enriched with microbiological additives.

During the discussion, farmers actively engaged in exchanging experiences and voicing concerns. The most prominent concern is related to product safety, particularly the potential presence of harmful substances such as antibiotics, heavy metals, or other contaminants in fertilisers made from sewage sludge.

These concerns reflected a general need for:

- Transparent and easily accessible data on product safety and composition,
- Clear regulatory standards ensuring that alternative fertilisers meet high environmental and health protection criteria,
- Further research and demonstration efforts to build trust and demonstrate long-term impacts on soil quality and crop yield.

Pictures of event

Farmers participating in the meeting

3.2.3 Group visit 3

General information

Region:	Poland
Date of Visit:	13.03.2025
Number of farmer attendees:	10

Relevant information/material used

As part of the 3rd NOVAFERT study visit on the 13th of March 2025, a group of farmers gathered to explore the project's objectives, methodologies, and current developments in the field of alternative fertilisers. Meetings were held within two consecutive days because of a visit size restriction on site. The visit began with a comprehensive presentation introducing the goals of the NOVAFERT project, with particular focus on the sustainable use of secondary raw materials in fertiliser production. Emphasis was placed on the importance of closing nutrient loops and supporting local value chains through innovative, waste-based solutions.

Key topics addressed during the session included:

- Assessment methodologies developed within NOVAFERT for evaluating the production, storage, distribution, and application of alternative fertilisers;
- Environmental and socio-economic impact analyses to assess the sustainability of fertiliser products.
- Identification and mapping of secondary raw materials used across participating countries.
- Presentation of core project outputs, including the *Atlas of Nutrient-Oriented Living Labs* and a dedicated database of waste-based value chains, supporting knowledge sharing and best practice exchange.

A central part of the session was devoted to a detailed case study of **Glebex+**, an innovative soil improver produced from thermally dried sewage sludge by the wastewater treatment plant in Rzeszów, Poland. The following aspects of the product were highlighted:

- The production process.
- The chemical composition of Glebex+.
- The physical characteristics of the product.
- The product's cost-effectiveness, making it a competitive option compared to conventional fertilisers.

Participants showed strong interest in the topic and engaged actively during the discussion session. Many shared positive experiences with alternative fertilisers while also expressing caution regarding products derived from sewage sludge. Common concerns included the potential presence of contaminants such as heavy metals, pharmaceutical residues, or microplastics—issues that call for transparent quality control measures and clear regulatory guidance.

The visit concluded with a reflection session and the distribution of a survey. The insights gathered will contribute to refining NOVAFERT's activities and ensuring that project outcomes align with the real-world needs of farmers in the agriculture sector.

Pictures of event

Participants of the 3rd meeting

3.2.4 Group visit 4

General information

Region:	Poland
Date of Visit:	26.03.2025
Number of farmer attendees:	14

Relevant information/material used

As part of the 4th NOVAFERT study visit on 26th of March 2025, farmers and relevant stakeholders were introduced to the objectives and ongoing developments of the NOVAFERT project. The presentation was delivered by Ms Paulina Marcinek (MEERI PAS).

The session covered the following key aspects:

- An overview of the NOVAFERT project's objectives, including the development of assessment methodologies for the production, storage, distribution and application of alternative fertilisers.
- Life Cycle Analysis (LCA, LCCA, S-LCA) of fertiliser products, with a focus on their environmental impact.
- Identification of target secondary raw materials utilised in participating countries, such as sewage sludge, digestate, animal manure or biowaste.
- Presentation of current results, including the development of an Atlas of nutrient-oriented Living Labs and a database of waste-based value chains.

A significant portion of the presentation focused on showcasing best practices, particularly the case of Glebex+, produced from sewage sludge by the WWTP in Rzeszów, Poland. The following aspects were highlighted:

- The production process, including thermal drying of sludge at 130 C⁰ and enrichment with microbiological preparation.
- The chemical composition of the product, featuring nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium and organic matter content.
- The physical characteristics of the product (solid, granulated form, >90% dry matter) and its applicability across various sectors, including arable crops, ornamental plants, and grasslands.

Following the presentation, a discussion session was held during which farmers had the opportunity to ask questions and share experiences related to the use of fertilisers derived from secondary raw materials. The meeting concluded with the distribution of a survey, designed to collect feedback and suggestions for the further development of the NOVAFERT project.

Pictures of event

Good practices presented by Paulina Marcinek

3.2.5 Group visit 5

General information

Region:	Poland
Date of Visit:	31.03.2025
Number of farmer attendees:	11

Relevant information/material used

As part of the final NOVAFERT meeting held on 31st of March 2025, a group of 11 farmers took part in an interactive session aimed at deepening their understanding of sustainable fertilisation practices and exploring alternatives to conventional inputs.

The session began with an introduction to the goals of the NOVAFERT project, highlighting the promotion of circular economy principles through the development and application of fertilisers based on secondary raw materials. Participants were also introduced to the environmental assessment methods used within the projects, such as Life Cycle Analysis (LCA) and related approaches, which demonstrate how the environmental footprint of fertiliser products can be measured and improved.

The meeting focused on the practical implications of using waste-derived fertilisers. In this context, a case study of Glebex+—a granulated soil improver produced from thermally dried municipal sewage sludge—was presented. The case study covered the following key elements:

- The production process and input materials.
- The chemical profile of the product.
- Its potential applications.

Farmers responded with a high level of engagement, sharing their own fertilisation strategies, experiences with organic inputs, and opinions on integrating waste-based products into their current systems. The meeting concluded with an open discussion, during which participants exchanged views and asked follow-up questions.

Pictures of event

Participant filling in the NOVAFERT survey

4. Lighthouse demonstration – Finland

Manure and food processing side streams (biowaste) are among the main nutrient-rich side streams utilized as an alternative fertiliser in Finland. Anaerobic digestion is the main manure treatment method, and separation afterwards is commonly conducted to separate solid and liquid fractions, representing phosphorus and nitrogen-rich fractions, respectively.

Pirteä Porsas Ltd., located in Vehmaa, southwest Finland, processes about 16,000 m³ of pig slurry (1600 sows) annually, with a capacity up to 35000 m³. After anaerobic digestion, the slurry is separated into liquid and solid fractions. The liquid fraction is distributed to fields via pipelines extending up to 4 km from the digester, while the solid fraction, rich in phosphorus (P), is used on fields needing P fertilization. By concentrating phosphorus (P) into the solid fraction, transportation costs to fields needing this nutrient are reduced.

This method ensures that fields with high P status only receive the liquid fraction, helping to reduce excessive soil P levels and potential P losses to surface waters. The technology for distributing the liquid fraction through pipelines is innovative in Finland. It reduces farm-to-field traffic by pumping the liquid close to the fields, where it is applied using umbilical slurry spreading before sowing spring or winter cereals. This method can also be used for winter cereals in early spring. Slurry spreading can be conducted on a grass stand as well.

Figure 7. Application of slurry using an umbilical system for the grass stand.

4.1 Type of fertiliser/s being tested and demonstrated

An anaerobically digested and separated liquid fraction of pig slurry is tested and demonstrated as an alternative nitrogen fertilizer. Demonstration is conducted on a field having a high phosphorus status that does not require extra addition for optimal yield.

Biobased fertilizers are demonstrated in field trials that are part of EU-project DeliSoil. Due to practical and logistical reasons, it was not possible to hold all lighthouse demonstrations on site. Therefore, where it was not possible to host farmers at the lighthouse demonstration site information regarding the system was disseminated at other relevant events/locations.

4.1.1 Application strategies for fertiliser

Liquid fraction of pig slurry is injected into the soil, which decreases ammonia volatilisation and thus increases nutrient use efficiency. Biowaste is incorporated into the soil before sowing.

4.1.2 Cost analysis and mineral fertiliser replacement value for alternative fertiliser/s

No information is available on this product for now. This work will be completed in the coming months as part of the Nutribudget EU project.

4.2 Details and evidence of the five farmer group visits to the lighthouse demonstration site

4.2.1 Group visit 1

General information

Region: Vehmaa	Finland
Date of Visit:	15.8.2024
Number of farmer attendees:	24 attendees, including farmers, policymakers, food and fertiliser companies, industry associations, and NGOs

Relevant information/material used

A stakeholder event was held at the premises of Pirteä Porsas Ltd. During the event, the Novafert project was presented to the audience. This was followed by an introduction to the field trial site, where the liquid fraction of digested pig slurry is used as a nitrogen fertilizer. Yara's Atfarm technology was employed to correct potential nitrogen deficiencies when the barley reached the stem elongation stage.

Pictures of event

Introduction of Novafert project (left) and field trial site (right) where the liquid fraction of pig slurry is used as N fertilizer.

4.2.2 Group visit 2

General information

Region: Jokioinen	Finland
Date of Visit:	29.8.2025
Number of farmer attendees:	31 attendees including policy makers (both local and national administration), researchers, and NGOs.

Relevant information/material used

Luke hosted a demo day to introduce biowaste and manure as potential starting materials for alternative fertilizers. The event was organized jointly by the DeliSoil and Novafert projects. During the event, the Novafert project was introduced, and participants visited "Biopaja," where Luke has facilities for producing alternative fertilizers using various technologies. A field visit was also conducted to present trials testing different types of alternative fertilizers, including those based on manure and biowaste.

Pictures of event

Farmers visiting facilities including field application

4.2.3 Group visits 3, 4 and 5

General information

Region: Oripää

Finland

Date of Visit: 2–5 July 2025

Number of farmer attendees: Over 500 people visited the Luke stand, including a representative from the Novafert project. These included farmers, policymakers, food and fertiliser companies, industry associations, NGOs, and families

Relevant information/material used

OKRA is one of the largest farm fairs in Finland. Held in Oripää, South-Western Finland, from 2 to 5 July 2025, the event attracted hundreds of exhibitors and thousands of visitors. In 2025, OKRA welcomed around 20,000 visitors per day. OKRA showcases the latest innovations in agriculture, forestry, farm machinery, cattle breeding, as well as dairy and poultry production. Several consultants, research organisations, and administrative bodies were present to provide up-to-date information for professionals. Large corporations and small producers had the opportunity to exhibit and sell their products.

LUKE hosted a stand at the fair, with the Novafert banner. Novafert project presented six different recycled fertilisers, both organic- and mineral-based, including struvite, Monterra, EcoPlant Humi, Bioagenasol, Optisol, and MBM. The display of recycled fertilisers attracted significant interest. Visitors to the stand recognised the importance of nutrient recycling, and many discussions focused on the role of recycled fertilisers in maintaining soil fertility. Sewage sludge-based fertilisers raised concerns about contamination, highlighting the need to build trust and promote clear safety standards.

Pictures of event

Sample fertilisers that are being used in the lighthouse demonstration

Attendees visiting the Luke stand regarding alternative fertilisers

5. Lighthouse demonstration – Flanders (BE)

The lighthouse demo events organized in Flanders have provided valuable opportunities for showcasing the latest innovations in circular fertilizers and sustainable agricultural practices. Two major field demonstration events were held at key agricultural locations, including a farmer's field where Inagro conducted trials which is the lighthouse demonstration site selected in the NOVAFERT project, and the Bottelare Experimental Farm, where UGent and Inagro collaborated to showcase ongoing field trials. These trials, which explored various sustainable products including pig urine, liquid fraction of digestate, ammonium salts, and mineral concentrates, demonstrated the effectiveness of circular fertilizers in real-world agricultural settings. Additionally, the trial field visit on August 13, 2024, offered insights into circular fertilizers and their role in meeting the RENURE legislation requirements. During this event, attendees gained firsthand knowledge of how these fertilizers performed in comparison to conventional options, including results from potato trials using innovative blends and zeolite combinations. The demo events also highlighted the integration of technology in fertilizer production, featuring presentations from technology processing companies that are pivotal in transforming organic waste into valuable fertilizers. Notably, NURESYS conducted a visual demonstration of their struvite processing unit, which extracts phosphorus from potato processing water. Through these demos, stakeholders from various sectors, agriculture, technology, and policy, were able to connect and explore how circular fertilizers can support both environmental and economic sustainability in the agricultural industry. Building on these efforts, a third demonstration event was held on May 8, 2025, at the INAGRO site in Rumbeke-Beitem. This event focused specifically on the field application of biobased soil improvers, with an emphasis on a frass-struvite pellet formulation.

5.1 Type of fertiliser/s being tested and demonstrated

Table 6. fertiliser type and nutrient composition used in Flanders

Bio-based fertiliser	Mineral composition	Feedstock
Ammoniumsulphate	P<0.000038, K<0.000021 NH ₄ ⁺ -N= 42.3 ± 3.49 NO ₃ ⁻ -N= 1.4 ± 0.08	Waste water
Ammoniumsulphate + zeolites	P=0.04 ± 0.00 K= 12 ± 0.96 NH ₄ ⁺ -N= 12.3 ± 0.44 NO ₃ ⁻ -N= 0.4 ± 0.08	Waste water
Mineral concentrate	Total N: 1.6% Total P: 0.371% Total K: 2,1% Total Ca: 0,17% Total Mg: 0.034%	
Biological scrubber water + mineral concentrate	N: 4603,1 mg/L P: 21,4 mg/L K: 4496,9 mg/L S: 1862,8 mg/L	Manure
Ammonium sulphate + mineral concentrate	N: 7841,2mg/L P: 6,38 mg/L K: 9507,17 mg/L S: 8545,09 mg/L	Manure
Pig urine + mineral concentrate	N: 5665,53 mg/L P: 25,63 mg/L K: 4997,76 mg/L S: 820,74 mg/L	Pig urine and manure

Liquid fraction pig digestate + mineral concentrate	N: 1326 mg/L P: 33,78 mg/L K: 7773,51 mg/L S: 347,58 mg/L	manure
Frass POM, N Struvite	Org. C (%): 25.42 N (%): 2.29 P2O5 (%):6.68 K2O (%):6.71 Ca (%):2.53 Mg (%):2.79 S (%):0.11	Frass POM: Frass produced by insects reared on a diet of 50% dry alperujo (olive pomace) and 50% mixed grains Struvite from potato processing waste water

5.1.1 Application strategies for fertiliser

Mixing of zeolites and ammonium sulphate was done in a ratio of 1 litre of AS per 2,34kg of zeolites. The synthetic fertiliser and mix of zeolites with ammonium sulphate were applied by hand and tilled into the soil. In the treatment with just ammonium sulphate, it was injected into the soil with a field trial fertiliser machine. The frass-struvite soil improver is formulated in pellet form and was applied directly by hand during the field demonstration.

5.1.2 Cost analysis and mineral fertiliser replacement value for alternative fertiliser/s

Information is not available

5.2 Details and evidence of the five farmer group visits to the lighthouse demonstration site

5.2.1 Group visit 1

General information

Region: CAUWENTYNESTRAAT 12, WINGENE	Flanders
Date of Visit:	13/08/2024
Number of farmer attendees:	32

Relevant information/material used

- 1) Project Introduction:** Presented printed slide decks to introduce the project, emphasizing its relevance and objectives.
- 2) Fertilizer Application Demonstration:** Showcased the injector to illustrate the method of fertilizer application in a practical context.
- 3) Field Trial Tour:** Inagro led participants through the trial plots where RENURE-based products (Ammonium Sulphate) and certain other blends of products (give example) and conventional fertilisers were compared, highlighting differences and responses relative to synthetic fertilizers.
- 4) Product Characterization & Experimental Setup:** Distributed printed slides explaining product properties, the experimental design, and expected outcomes
- 5) RENURE Criteria & Products:** Provided booklets and printed slides explaining RENURE requirements and demonstrated sample products to give participants a tangible understanding.

Pictures of event

Farmers visiting the lighthouse demonstration site

5.2.2 Group visit 2

General information

Region: Bottelare	Flanders
Date of Visit:	June 20 th 2024
Number of farmer attendees:	35

Relevant information/material used

Slides-Overview of Novafert

- Brief introduction to the project and its goal

Novafert Flyer and Roll-Up

Ongoing Experiment Overview

- Introduce the experiment being conducted on the farm, detailing the experimental design (e.g., control group using synthetic fertilizer).
- Mention the duration of the experiment and the crops being tested.
- Highlight the methodology: how the fertilizers are applied, frequency of application, and monitoring protocols.

Crop Results: Biobased fertiliser vs. Synthetic Fertilizer

- Present visual data of plant height, leaf size, and other indicators of crop health
- Graphs or charts comparing the yield from the control group

Pictures of event

Greenhouse demonstration site

5.2.3 Group visit 3

General information

Region: Drongen

Flanders

Date of Visit: 20 January, 2025

Number of farmer attendees:34

Relevant information/material used

Slide 1: Project Overview

- Mention specific goals, outputs and how these align with the interests of local stakeholders (e.g., local farmers, businesses, policymakers).

Slide 2: LCA (Life Cycle Assessment) Analysis of the Product

Detailed Explanation of the Products

- Provide a clear and detailed explanation of the biobased fertilizer products being presented (struvite)

Video: Visual Representation of the Technology Processing Unit

- A short video that visually demonstrates the technology behind the production of biobased fertiliser.
Explain the environmental benefits of the production process itself, including energy use, waste reduction, and emissions control.

Pictures of event

Farmers receiving information regarding the lighthouse demonstration site

5.2.4 Group visit 4

General information

Region: Inagro	Flanders
Date of Visit:	08/05/2025
Number of farmer attendees:	20

Relevant information/material used

The demonstration event was supported by a range of targeted materials and structured activities to inform and engage stakeholders. Slide presentations were used to convey detailed product information, including the origin and characterisation of the biobased fertilisers, their composition, and their expected agronomic functions. Physical samples of the frass-struvite pellets, formulated as ready-to-use soil improvers, were displayed and handled by participants, allowing them to assess the product's form and quality directly. Project flyers and roll-up banners provided on-site visuals to reinforce the core

messages and increase visibility of the broader project goals. During the field visit, the application strategy was demonstrated manually, showing how the pellets were applied by hand. Stakeholders were also guided through the layout of different treatment plots, with explanations on the rationale behind each treatment (e.g., single vs. combined inputs) and early field observations regarding crop response and soil condition. This combination of visual aids, live demonstration, and scientific context aimed to strengthen understanding and confidence in the tested biobased solutions

Pictures of event

Farmers visiting the lighthouse demonstration site

6. Lighthouse demonstration – Andalusia (SP)

The Andalusian lighthouse demo is the so-called “Living Lab La Axarquía”, created and maintained by Bioazul in the framework of different EU-funded projects. It is located in Algarrobo municipality, Malaga province, Andalusia region, Spain.

La Axarquía region gathers 31 municipalities (224,400 inhabitants) in the province of Malaga in Southern Spain and is the main producer of subtropical crops in Europe. It combines rural areas in the interior with strong agricultural activity and densely populated coastal areas with high affluence of tourists during the summer. The region suffers from water scarcity with overexploitation of groundwater, low levels of water reservoirs, and is at risk of desertification.

La Viñuela is the reservoir providing water to La Axarquía region. With a capacity of 156 Hm³, it accounts for 36 Hm³ at this moment (21.82% of its capacity); although being too low, the situation is much better than last year, which by the same time of the year accounted for 12 Hm³ (7.27% of its capacity).

With regards to the concrete location in which the living lab is located, Algarrobo, the summers are hot, arid, and mostly clear, and the winters are windy and partly cloudy. Over the course of the year, the temperature varies from 7°C to 31°C and is rarely below 3°C or above 34°C. On the other hand, Algarrobo experiences significant seasonal variation in monthly rainfall. The month with the biggest amount of rain in Algarrobo is November, with an average rainfall of 57 mm. The month with the least rain in Algarrobo is July, with an average rainfall of 1 mm.

Due to the location of the living lab, the crops there are very frequently subjected to strong winds that blow from the West and the East, causing damage like falling leaves and micro wounds, which are entry points for fungi such as those that cause the dieback of branches.

As episodes of torrential rain become more frequent, the amounts of water that accumulate can become very large, thus posing a serious risk for the crops and the infrastructures (irrigation manholes, service roads, etc.).

The Living Lab La Axarquía was established in 2015 thanks to the H2020 project Richwater[®], whose main objective was to validate a technology based on a membrane bioreactor that was able to produce an effluent with quality enough to be used in agricultural irrigation. In addition, it included a nutrient optimisation process to fertigate the crops, what was definitely very beneficial for the farmers, as this way they could reduce the number of chemical fertilisers to be added to their soils.

The experimental plot located next to the wastewater treatment plant, where RichWater[®] system was also installed, was used to develop agronomic tests in collaboration with IHSM La Mayora Institute, a national research institution. In these studies, the quality and productivity of the crops (tomatoes in this case) irrigated with reclaimed water were analysed, concluding there were no significant differences with those produced traditionally.

RichWater® project was a milestone in R&D&I with reclaimed water and attracted the interest of numerous actors in the region who, since then, have played a very relevant role in the continuity of the project. The collaboration with the Algarrobo City Council, the Association of Municipalities of Axarquía Costa del Sol, the Community of Irrigators of Algarrobo, Trops (a big fruits and vegetables producer and distributor), Axaragua (the municipal company in charge of water management in the region) and the Spanish Association of Tropical Crops, among others, has been essential to continue betting on the sustainability of the agricultural sector in La Axarquía.

Thanks to the collaboration of all these agents, the experimental plot has become what we nowadays know as the "Living Lab La Axarquía", recognised by Water Europe (the European Water Platform), which has included RichWater® in their EU Water-oriented Living Labs Atlas.

Since then, the Living Lab La Axarquía has been the center of various initiatives; currently, Bioazul leads and coordinates three innovation projects with demonstration activities in the Living Lab:

- In Bonex project (PRIMA project), Bioazul is studying the nutritional content of reclaimed water to develop a decision tool that helps farmers calculate the optimal number of additional fertilisers to be added when fertigating with reclaimed water. This is important to both reduce the number of chemical fertilisers to be used, and also to protect the soil, as the nutrient content in reclaimed water could constitute an environmental risk if its production and use is not properly managed.
- In P2Green project (Horizon Europe project), RichWater®'s agronomic studies with tomatoes have been expanded to subtropical crops, which constitute a key source of income in the Axarquía region. In addition, the work done in Bonex with the nutrient management tool is being enriched thanks to the addition of NPK sensors in the soil to provide a more automated solution.
- In Axarquía Sostenible project (regional operational group), P2Green studies have been expanded to other subtropical crops, such as passion fruit and dragon fruit. In addition, the Bonex nutrient management tool is being also complemented with data extracted from foliar studies and sap analyses.

The living lab currently counts with the production of approximately 3650 m³/year of reclaimed water (nutrient-rich effluent) generated by the treatment of Algarrobo's municipal wastewater, Andalusia's assigned secondary raw material for research in the Novafert context. This reclaimed water (Andalusia's alternative fertiliser) serves to fertigate subtropical crops, which are widely cultivated in the region. Concretely, 120 avocado and mango trees (60 avocado (Hass) and 60 mango (Osteen)) are part of the study. In addition, 12 dragon and passion fruit (6 dragon fruit (Townsend Pink) and 6 passion fruit (P. edulis f. edulis x colvilli)) have been fertigated in an additional greenhouse study.

Total size of facilities: 0.2 ha (2000 m²) approximately.

- Outdoor area with avocado and mango: 838 m².
 - o Avocado plot: 238 m².

- Mango plot: 600 m².
- Greenhouse with passion fruit and dragon fruit: 200 m².

Figure 8. Andalusian lighthouse demo aerial photograph and items description

The majority of the soil of the Living Lab corresponds to sandy loam soil, while in some parts of the mangoes area, soil is just loamy. The organic matter percentage is 0,66%, and the average pH is 8,6. Both organic matter and pH have minimal spatial variations.

Figure 9. Living Lab La Axarquía soil composition

Bioazul's water reclamation system

Bioazul's mixing station

Dragon and passion fruit crops in the greenhouse area

Dragon and passion fruit crops in the greenhouse area

Dragon fruit crops in the greenhouse area

Passion fruit crops in the greenhouse area

Mango crops in the open area

Mango crops in the open area

Mango crops in the open area: treatment line 1

Mango crops in the open area: treatment line 2

Mango crops in the open area: treatment line 3

Avocado crops in the open area

Avocado crops in the open area

Avocado crops in the open area

6.1 Type of fertiliser/s being tested and demonstrated

The fertiliser used as alternative to the chemical ones is reclaimed water (treated water in which nutrients have been concentrated), which is used for fertigation. This way, crops are nourished at the same time they are hydrated, and thus the need of adding external chemical fertilisers becomes smaller or even null for some nutrients.

Figure 10. Living Lab La Axarquía water reclamation and fertigation process

6.1.1 Application strategies for fertiliser

There are different application strategies in outdoor and indoor areas:

- 1) Outdoor area:

Three different fertigation treatments are applied to each type of crop (mango and avocado):

- T1) Control treatment (well water + conventional fertilisation).

- T2) Reclaimed water without fertilisation.
- T3) Smart irrigation (reclaimed water with adjusted fertilisation).

In addition to this, a nutrient management tool and decision support system has been implemented, and it includes a set of lysimeters, agricultural tensiometer, sensors and transducers, iDatacloud and iTelemeter (I/O controllers).

Figure 11. Living Lab La Axarquía outdoor area application strategies

2) Greenhouse (multi-channel greenhouse with concrete floor):

Two different fertigation treatments are applied to each type of crop (dragon fruit and passion fruit):

- T1) Control treatment (well water + conventional fertilisation).
- T2) Reclaimed water without fertilisation.

Figure 12. Living Lab La Axarquía indoor area application strategies

6.1.2 Cost analysis and mineral fertiliser replacement value for alternative fertiliser/s

When using this reclaimed water, the amount needed of chemical fertilisers is smaller. Some data on the fertilising behaviour of the reclaimed water produced are shown below.

Table 7. Percentage of nutritional demand covered per NPK of reclaimed water:

Mango	% supplied	Avocado	% supplied
N	72	N	79
P	No data	P	No data
K	143	K	102

Table 8. Amount of chemical fertilisers saved thanks to the use of reclaimed water for avocado and mango:

Avocado					
Month	Fertiliser	Before (g/tree)	After (g/tree)	Savings (%)	Fertilisers eliminated
June	Nitrato potásico	17	2.24	86.82%	Solución de calcio (8 g), Quelato de hierro (0.8 g), Ácido ortobórico (0.8 g)
	Nitrato amónico	16	9.12	43.00%	
July	Nitrato potásico	17	2.02	88.12%	Solución de calcio (8 g), Quelato de hierro (0.8 g), Ácido ortobórico (0.8 g)
	Nitrato amónico	16	9.00	43.75%	
August	Nitrato potásico	17	2.02	88.12%	Solución de calcio (8 g), Quelato de hierro (0.8 g), Ácido ortobórico (0.8 g)
	Nitrato amónico	16	9.00	43.75%	
September	Nitrato potásico	17	2.24	86.82%	Ácido ortobórico (0.8 g)
	Nitrato amónico	16	8.43	47.31%	
October	Nitrato potásico	17	2.47	85.47%	Ácido ortobórico (0.8 g)

	Nitrato amónico	16	8.55	46.56%	
November	Nitrato potásico	17	2.70	84.12%	Ácido ortobórico (0.8 g)
	Nitrato amónico	16	8.66	45.88%	
Mango					
Month	Fertiliser	Before (g/tree)	After (g/tree)	Savings (%)	Fertilisers eliminated
April	Nitrato amónico	9	10.45	-16.11% (Increase)	Solución de calcio (24 g) – completely eliminated, Quelato de hierro (4 g) – completely eliminated
May	Nitrato amónico	9	10.25	-13.89% (Increase)	Solución de calcio (24 g) – completely eliminated, Quelato de hierro (4 g) – completely eliminated
June	Nitrato amónico	9	8	11.11%	Nitrato de calcio (12 g) – completely eliminated, Sulfato de zinc (25 g) – completely eliminated
July	Nitrato amónico	9	8	11.11%	Nitrato de calcio (12 g) – completely eliminated
August	Nitrato amónico	9	8	11.11%	Nitrato de calcio (12 g) – completely eliminated
September	Nitrato amónico	9	8	11.11%	Nitrato de calcio (12 g) – completely eliminated

Table 9. Economic savings thanks to using reclaimed water for avocado and mango:

Treatment	Avocado (€/ha/year)	Mango (€/ha/year)
Local	290	1072
Reclaimed	60	345
Savings (€/ha/year)	230	727
Savings (%)	79.31	80.77

- Economic savings thanks to using reclaimed water for dragon fruit and passion fruit:

Month	Savings €/hectare	
	Dragon fruit	Passion fruit
January	3,52	23,54
February	3,52	35,31
March	3,74	23,54
April	6,6	35,31
May	6,6	58,85
June	5,94	70,62
July	10,78	70,62
August	16,06	70,62
September	13,42	117,7
October	8,8	23,54
November	5,94	11,77
December	5,94	11,77
Total	90,2	541,42

Some impacts of using this alternative fertiliser have been identified at the environmental level, like the reduction of diffuse pollution of surface and groundwater due to agricultural activity and overuse of mineral fertilisers.

In addition, reclaimed water constitutes a constant and reliable source of water for irrigation (independent of climate events, e.g., droughts) and net increase of water sources in coastal areas (with treated ww discharged to the sea), what also leads to the preservation of drinking water sources (e.g., groundwater, water reservoir, etc.).

However, some difficulties have been encountered as well for their application, including legal and economic aspects. Administrative procedures are too long and complicated, and although it is possible to generate reclaimed water in the region, it is not easy to get the enabling title to use it in the short or even medium term.

In this sense, the coordination between national and regional administrations would be crucial. Besides the differences between the National and Andalusian governments, there are other institutions managing water concessions, like the water basin management authorities. Although the competencies over these management authorities belong to the National Government, coordination should be fostered among them to unify the criteria of water reuse in the regions where they coexist.

In addition, it would be necessary to regularise the irrigation communities, encouraging farmers to associate with more efficient and controlled water management.

Novafert

Finally, public acceptance is always an aspect to be considered. That is why it is essential to promote the positive aspects of using reclaimed water, including the healthiness and safety of the food produced with this resource.

6.2 Details and evidence of the five farmer group visits to the lighthouse demonstration site

6.2.1 Group visit 1

General information

Region:	Andalusia
Date of Visit:	20/06/2024
Number of farmer attendees:	30 participants (researchers, farmers, members from the irrigation community, members of the city council, representatives from regional related companies, etc.)

Relevant information/material used

On June 20th, 2024, a demo visit was organised in collaboration with P2Green project (also funded by Horizon Europe). It was focused on the future of reclaimed water for agricultural use and the use of smart fertigation tools.

30 participants embarked on a guided tour across our test site, offering a first-hand look at:

- The treatment process at the Algarrobo municipal wastewater treatment plant.
- The water reclamation facility producing reclaimed water for irrigation.
- Avocado and mango crops are used to test various fertigation treatments.
- The development of an innovative smart fertigation tool.

This collaborative effort marks a significant step towards sustainable water management and agricultural practices in La Axarquía and beyond.

Pictures of event

Farmers visiting the lighthouse demonstration site

6.2.2 Group visit 2

General information

Region:	Andalusia
Date of Visit:	08/10/2024
Number of farmer attendees:	40 senior agronomy students

Relevant information/material used

On October 8th, our Living Lab in La Axarquía welcomed 40 senior agronomy students from Chapingo University in Mexico. This visit, organised by BIOAZUL in collaboration with CSIC-IHSM La Mayora and TROPS, aimed to inform students about the innovative projects based at the Algarrobo demonstration plot and to explain the different lines of work and research underway regarding the use of reclaimed water in subtropical crops. The students learned about the Living Lab concept thanks to the Horizon Europe project NOVAFERT, which aims to promote the use of alternative fertilisers, being focused in Andalusia region on wastewater as secondary raw material for nutrients recovery, which is the process developed in this Living Lab of La Axarquía. Some other projects coexist with NOVAFERT in this Living Lab. As part of the "Axarquía Sostenible" Operational Group, attendees were able to witness firsthand the state of the pitaya and passion fruit crops in the greenhouse. The pitaya plants are currently in full bloom, a significant step in evaluating the use of reclaimed water and the production of this crop. Additionally, the students visited the outdoor area dedicated to avocado and mango crops, part of the Horizon Europe project P2GreenN. Since May 2023, various fertigation treatments have been carried out on the plot, using both reclaimed water and local water. Recently, the TROPS team completed pruning tasks for avocados and mangoes, a crucial step to promote tree growth and future fruit production. Furthermore, students learned about the tertiary treatment and disinfection processes used to produce reclaimed water from urban wastewater. It was a day filled with enthusiasm from the participants, packed with questions and answers, in an atmosphere of great interest and support for the innovative work carried out by all the entities involved in each project.

Pictures of event

Farmers visiting the lighthouse demonstration site

6.2.3 Group visit 3

General information

Region:	Andalusia
Date of Visit:	22/11/2024
Number of farmer attendees:	40 commerce and administration students

Relevant information/material used

On November 22nd, 40 Commerce and Administration students from ESSCA, concretely from the Humanistic Management course, visited our Living Lab in La Axarquía to discover practical approaches to addressing global sustainability challenges. This visit was organised by BIOAZUL, that focused on the critical issue of water scarcity, especially in agriculture, and concretely in this area, so hit by drought. The students were taught on the Living Lab concept and how different research processes are taking place using the same space, how they complement and feed each other. In this sense, several projects like NOVAFERT, P2GreenN, Axarquía Sostenible or Boost-In were introduced. The students learnt how reclaimed water is used as alternative fertiliser in the living lab, fertigating avocados and mangoes in one sector on the living lab, and pitaya and passion fruit in another sector of the living lab (a greenhouse). It is important to highlight that La Axarquía is a subtropical region located 40 km away from Malaga, with ideal agro-climatic factors for the production of tropical fruit, thus with high water needs. The use of reclaimed water has a double purpose: looking for an alternative source of water and reducing the number of chemical fertilisers needed, while reducing the environmental impact

Pictures of event

Participants visiting the site

6.2.5 Group visit 5

General information

Region:	Andalusia
Date of Visit:	26/06/2025
Number of farmer attendees:	11 participants (farmers, citizens, researchers, companies in the sector)

Relevant information/material used

On June 26th, a group of 11 participants from the 4th Seminar of the International Forum for the Exchange of Sustainable Practices in Organic Production—organised by the Agroecology Partnership in Andalusia and funded by the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD) took part in a complementary technical visit to the Axarquía Living Lab in Algarrobo, Málaga. This visit, facilitated by Bioazul, offered an enriching additional opportunity for attendees to experience a real-life innovation hub focused on the safe and efficient use of reclaimed water as an alternative fertilising product for fertigation in agriculture. During the visit, participants toured the living lab and observed sustainable practices for water reuse, crop management, and irrigation efficiency in a region heavily affected by water scarcity. The use of reclaimed water for fertigation, a central focus of the Axarquía Living Lab, was presented as a viable solution to enhance resilience in Mediterranean agricultural systems.

Pictures of event

Novafert

Farmers visiting the lighthouse demonstration site

7. Lighthouse demonstration – Catalonia - (SP)

Fertinagro Biotech is a leading company in the development of innovative fertilisers designed to enhance agricultural productivity while ensuring environmental sustainability. With a strong commitment to efficiency, resource and logistics optimisation, the company provides advanced fertilisation solutions tailored to the specific needs of crops and soil.

Through continuous research and innovation, Fertinagro Biotech strives to improve nutrient use efficiency, reduce environmental impact, and promote sustainable agricultural practices. Its global presence and strategic partnerships enable the company to adapt to market demands, offering high-quality products that support farmers in achieving higher yields with a lower ecological footprint. Fertinagro Biotech operates through a diversified network of 22 subsidiaries strategically located worldwide, enabling its presence in over 90 countries.

The company, headquartered in Teruel, Aragón, operates several production plants in the NOVAFERT Catalonia-Aragon region:

- **Escucha (Teruel):**
[Fertinagro Organia S.L.U.](#) specializes in the manufacturing, distribution, and commercialization of organic, organo-mineral, and ecological fertilizers, as well as special products and amendments in powder and pellet form. The plant covers 50,000 m², employs 42 workers, and has a production capacity of 120,000 tons per year.
- **Utrillas (Teruel):**
In 2021, Fertinagro Biotech inaugurated the largest biofertiliser production plant in Europe in Utrillas, [Fertinagro nutrigenia S.L.U.](#). With an investment of €26 million, the plant produces 5,000 tons of biofertilizers annually and has created 25 new jobs.
- **Fertilizantes del Ebro (Lleida):**
In 2021, Fertinagro Biotech acquired [Fertiebro](#) and invested in updating its facilities. Their main business is focused on manufacturing and application of saturated liquid (also as gel and suspension products) fertilisers with high nutritional concentration, biostimulants, correctors, conditioners and other specific nutritional fertilizers. Their production capacity increased from 7.000t/year to 55.000t/year of liquid fertilisers, while the current production capacity of the plant is 70.000 t/year. The plant currently employs 20 workers, and 30% of the raw materials they use in their manufacturing processes are from circular origin.

Fertinagro Biotech goes beyond fertiliser production by providing farmers with cutting-edge agronomic solutions and expert guidance. Through a team of over 200 agricultural technicians, the company offers Integrated Fertilisation Plans—customized fertilisation programs tailored to the specific needs of each crop and soil type.

These personalised strategies help more than 100,000 farmers across Spain maximise their yields and improve profitability in a sustainable way. Commonly, the customers are either highland owners working without intermediaries or small producers. In addition, the company developed a highly specialised commercial distribution network, working with over 500 distributors to ensure nationwide coverage.

This lighthouse demonstration aims to showcase the positive business model that Fertinagro Biotech developed, based mainly on circular bioeconomy principles, while promoting nutrient recovery, recycling, and sustainable agronomic practices. The production plant in Lleida (Catalonia) serves as the primary lighthouse demonstration site; however, visits to the facility are quite restricted and difficult to organise, and as a result only two visits could be managed during the final two years of the project. To complement this, an additional demonstration visit was organised at one of the farms where Fertibro tests its products, which is also recognised as a living lab under the Novafert initiative.

The positive outcome for the farmers includes not only the satisfactory agronomic performance but also soil health improvement and economic savings when they switch from conventional field management to the fertilisation plans developed by the technicians in Fertinagro.

Figure 13. Details of the manufacturing and application of the fertilisers produced in FERTIEBRO facilities. a) transportation belt of blended products; b) weight controlling loading hopper for products to be blended; c) FERTIEBRO solid blends ready to be delivered; d) recycled raw material as ingredient; e) liquid fertiliser spreader

7.1 Type of fertiliser/s being tested and demonstrated

The fertilisers showcased in the Catalonia- Aragon region lighthouse demonstration in NOVAFERT are the ones manufactured in FERTIEBRO facilities, focusing particularly on liquid fertilisers (liquid organo-mineral fertilisers). Nutrients and micronutrients included in their products are from recycled origin at a 30%, being mainly produced with animal (animal by-products) or plant by-products, although other industrial by-products with low market value are also efficiently used as nutrient sources. Amino acids are often included in FERTIEBRO formulations for biostimulant effect, and humic and fulvic acid-based products are also one of the most remarkable products they offer. The products are grouped as follows:

- Liquid NPK formulations (FERTABLI products): A portfolio of NPK formulations is offered with slight adjustments.
 - Neutral FERTABLI product is offered for its use in extensive crops which are applied using pivot machine or sprinkler system for fertilisation. Fertilisation is usually done in December and June. Formulations offered are 17-8-2 NPK or 18-4-4 NPK.
 - Acid FERTABLI is offered for fruit trees as nutrients are more efficiently absorbed from tree roots in acidic conditions. Formulations offered are: 2-2-12 which is more demanded in Catalonia, 2-4-12 which is more demanded in Aragon, 8-4-10 and 12- 4- 6. The FERTABLI products are applied through fertigation.
 - FERTABLI EFI is formulated similar to the previous ones, but they include a slight dosing of microelements and biostimulation effect.
 - FERTABLI Plus is formulated with the previous formulas with the addition of a 2% of amino acids (thus 12%N is added through amino acid addition). This product is highly efficient and their inclusion in fertilisation plans comes with the reduction in 20% of mineral fertilisation.

- Nitrogen-based formulations (NITROS products): These formulations include nitrogen and sulphur elements. There is a portfolio of formulations for extensive crops and fruit trees and among the products offered oligoelements might be added if customers are interested. Additionally, specific products for organic farming are also available in which the origin of the nitrogen is organic (animal by-products). The products might also include urease inhibitors to slow down nitrogen transformation once the products are applied, increasing their overall use efficiency.
 - Formulations for extensive crops. The formulations offered are 26+6 (NS); 24 + 8 (NS); 28 + 4 (NS). The formulations can include 2% of amino acids for their use in cereals of ryegrass which improves their growth. The products are offered in neutral pH.
 - Formulations for fruit trees. 20+ 10 (NS) formulation is offered for fruit trees. Addition of sulphur improves nitrogen use efficiency. The product is suggested to be used to prepare the trees to activate after winter and then, a small dose can be added post-harvest to prepare the tree for the winter.

- Some examples of nitrogen dosing and their distribution along the year might be for pear tree 85/100N units – 35 N units – 125 N units: for peach tree 85 N units – 35 N units - 130 N units.
- Potassium-based products: these products are potassium-acetate complexes which contain very low chloride. The formulations offered are 0-0-25 NPK and 0-0-15 NPK and are recommended for fruit trees to favor fruit sizing.
- Gel- based products: Gel formulations allow increasing the nutrient contents above the saturation point without precipitation. The formulations offered are: 20-5-5 NPK and 20-5-10 NPK.
- Correctors: correction with specific microelements: Correctors with magnesium, zinc, manganese, boron and combinations are offered. Their application can be foliar or radicular (fertigation or spray application), usually applied in spring. The formulations were developed to form microelement-lignosulfonate complexes which improves their absorption. As a specific example, Boron-Molibdene corrector is recommended for rapeseed and other flowering plants to be applied (foliar application) before blooming. They also offer correctors for organic producers, for instance they offer Boron 10 product for fruit trees, grapevines and vegetable crops.
- Special products:
 - AminoRed: This product contains 15% of amino acids and it is used for biostimulant effects. Normally the application dose recommended would be 2-4 kg/Ha for this specific product.
 - AcinRed: This product is a concentrated liquid product containing free amino acids (6%) and sulphur (14%). It also contains other microelements like iron and manganese. It is used to improve the root environment and improves the condition of the soil with excessive salt content. The application recommended is normally around 25 kg/Ha in spring and whenever there is excessive salt in soil and extra application at the beginning of summer. The product is normally applied through the irrigation system.
 - Tradihumus: It contains humic (3%) and fulvic (12%) acids to provide biostimulant and regenerative effect in soils, being able to activate the soil microbiome. It improves also the water holding capacity of soils which favors root development.
 - Tradisal: This product is equivalent to the previous AcinRed product, but it also contains 10% of calcium. This product is recommended as a soil conditioner for soils with high salinity or sub-optimal structure. It contains fulvic acid and calcium to displace the sodium ions through cationic exchange. Application is done through irrigation, and dosing should be distributed throughout the year.

Table 10. Description of product type used

Product	fertiliser
Fertabli neutral	NPK products
Fertabli acid	NPK products
Fertabli EFI	NPK products
Fertabli PLUS	NPK products
Nitros Duramon 26	Nitrogen-based products
Kaliumred 24	Potassium-based products
Kaliumred 25	Potassium-based products
Micrograma Mn	Corrector
Micrograma Mg	Corrector
Micrograma Zn	Corrector
Boro 10	Corrector
Micrograma B-Mo	Corrector
Micrograma Mn + Zn	Corrector
AminoRed	Special products
AcinRed	Special products
Tradihumus	Special products
Tradisal	Special products

7.1.1 Application strategies for fertiliser

The application strategy is determined by the product type. Most formulations, such as FERTILABI and NITROS, are applied via fertigation systems. Additionally, Fertinagro typically supplies growers with a tailored fertilization program, which is adjusted according to crop type, phenological stage, soil characteristics, and other agronomic factors.

7.1.2 Cost analysis and mineral fertiliser replacement value for alternative fertiliser/s

The cost of nutrients in alternative fertilisers depends on market conditions, with the price of raw materials playing a significant role. Typically, by-products are sourced at a low cost and formulated efficiently to maximize their agronomic effectiveness. The profit margin is determined by the purchase price of the by-product compared to the selling price of the final fertiliser. It is crucial to ensure that any processing or treatment of the material remains minimal to avoid excessive production costs while maintaining quality and efficiency. To illustrate the economic impact on farmers, a fertilisation plan can be used as an example. The cost of alternative fertilisers varies depending on their composition and the additional benefits they offer:

- Fertabli EFI (containing micronutrients and biostimulants) is priced at €30/t.
- Fertabli Plus, which includes 2% free amino acids, costs €60/t but provides farmers with a 20% reduction in mineral fertiliser use.
- Aminored, containing 15% amino acids, is available at €2/t. This significantly lower cost is due to Fertinagro's in-house production of amino acids, eliminating the need for external suppliers. This internal production strategy differentiates Fertinagro from its competitors, allowing them to maintain competitive pricing while enhancing the value of their products.

Farmers frequently choose these alternative fertilisers due to their cost-effectiveness and the additional benefits they provide, such as soil health improvement. Many companies also offer tailored fertilisation plans and dedicated agronomic support, further encouraging long-term adoption. This combination of economic viability, agronomic efficiency, and personalised service results in high farmer retention rates and reinforces the added value of these fertilisers in sustainable agricultural practices.

7.2 Details and evidence of the five farmer group visits to the lighthouse demonstration site

7.2.1 Group visit 1

General information

Region: Lleida	Catalonia
Date of Visit:	10th of October
Number of farmer attendees:	25

Relevant information/material used

- An introduction to the main objectives of the Novafert project was provided
- Participants visited the FertiEbro facilities, part of Fertinagro Biotech and designated as the NOVAFERT lighthouse site in the Catalan region. The visit provided participants with first-hand insight into advanced fertiliser manufacturing processes and circular innovations designed to foster more sustainable agricultural practices. Several bio-based fertilisers.

Pictures of the event

Farmers visiting the lighthouse demonstration

7.2.2 Group visit 2

General information

Region: Lleida,	Catalonia
Date of Visit:	20/05/2025
Number of farmer attendees:	20

Relevant information/material used

On May 20th NOVAFERT project organised a demo visit as part of its strategy to promote innovative solutions that support the use of recovered fertilizers.

The main activity was a site visit to the **Torre Santa María farm**, one of the project's living labs identified in the atlas for the Catalonia region. At this site, the company Sorigué is developing an on-farm biogas plant that enables the valorisation of livestock waste, and the production of innovative fertilizers derived from digestate. These fertilizers are subsequently applied to cereal crop fields.

The event was attended by more than 20 stakeholders from across the region. It included a series of presentations providing an overview of the NOVAFERT project and a review of other living labs identified in Catalonia. Sorigué presented their success story to other farmers and companies, explaining their path to the installation of the biogas plant, production of renewable energy that is injected into the network, and the valorization of digestate for application in their own cereal fields. The combination of technical knowledge, practical case studies, and open discussion among participants contributed to a valuable exchange of experiences.

Pictures of event

Farmers visiting the living lab

7.2.3 Group visit 3

General information

Region: Lleida, Catalonia
 Date of Visit: 17/06/2025
 Number of farmer attendees: 25

Relevant information/material used

As part of the NOVAFERT project, the third stakeholder demo visit in Catalonia was held on June 17, 2025, to support the co-creation and development of the Catalan Nutrients Platform. This initiative, identified as a key action in the **Regional Action Plan for the Catalan region**, aims to foster improved nutrient management and promote circular solutions in agriculture. The event focused on consolidating the progress made so far, sharing learnings from stakeholder engagement activities, and facilitating collective reflection on the platform’s organizational model, funding mechanisms, and strategic priorities.

Participants were presented with insights derived from NOVAFERT-led interviews and meetings with Catalan clusters and national technology platforms. These findings served as the basis for an open discussion on potential governance models for the platform. In addition, lessons learned from European nutrient management platforms were shared to inspire best practices and guide the Catalan initiative.

A participatory workshop followed, enabling stakeholders to collaboratively identify the platform’s priority activities, expected benefits for its members, and viable approaches to ensure its long-term self-sustainability.

To conclude the day, participants visited the FertiEbro facilities, part of Fertinagro Biotech, which is the **NOVAFERT lighthouse site in the Catalan region**. The visit offered a first-hand look at advanced fertilizer manufacturing processes and circular innovations aimed at achieving more sustainable agriculture. Several biobased fertilizers

Pictures of event

Participants in the event

8. Lighthouse demonstration – Croatia

In Croatia, the NOVAFERT Lighthouse demonstration is established **at the family-owned agricultural holding OPG Cenger, situated in Grubišno Polje**, a rural municipality in the continental region of Croatia characterised by diverse soils and mixed agricultural production.

Rooted in generations of agricultural tradition, family farm (OPG) Dario Cenger was established in 2005. Over time, its story expanded beyond local borders, evolving into a network of five successful businesses united under the Cenger Group. Each company within the group plays a distinct role while sharing a common mission: advancing ecological agriculture in Croatia. Bioel d.o.o. generates green energy through its 1MW biogas plant; PZ Zrno coordinates logistics and partnerships; Biodem handles distribution and sales; family farm (OPG) Jerko Cenger focuses on organic livestock farming, crop production, and the cultivation of medicinal plants; and family farm (OPG) Dario Cenger produces premium Ecodig organic fertilizer.

Operating as an integrated system, the companies within the Cenger Group follow a cooperative model, with family farm (OPG) Dario Cenger — the founder and Ecodig producer — at the core. This synergy fosters a unified approach to developing innovative agricultural solutions.

ECODIG, a certified top-tier ecological and organic fertiliser, features a well-balanced nutrient composition. This pH-neutral fertiliser is highly soluble, making it compatible with all soil types, and it promises to remarkably increase crop yields.

The primary objective of the Croatian Lighthouse demonstration is to evaluate the agronomic effectiveness, economic feasibility, and environmental benefits of using circular, bio-based fertilisers under real farm conditions. The Lighthouse showcases how certified organic fertilisers can be incorporated into conventional farming systems without disrupting operational workflows or requiring significant investment in new equipment. Through targeted nutrient management planning, these fertilisers are applied using standard agricultural machinery, ensuring ease of adoption and scalability for other farms in the region. This demonstration also provides a platform for farmer education and peer-to-peer learning. Field visits and workshops are used to share insights and practical experiences. These activities aim to build farmer confidence in alternative fertilisers and stimulate broader uptake in Croatia. In the broader context of the NOVAFERT project, the Croatian Lighthouse supports the overarching goals of nutrient circularity, fertiliser innovation, and regional knowledge exchange. By validating sustainable fertiliser solutions under practical farm conditions, the demonstration contributes to the transformation of agricultural practices toward more resilient, eco-efficient, and regenerative systems.

Figure 14. Ecodig facility

8.1 Type of fertiliser/s being tested and demonstrated

Ecodig fertilisers are created by anaerobic digestion of plant materials and manure from livestock production with the addition of a mineral component.

In the process of anaerobic digestion, during the breakdown of complex organic substances (e.g., carbohydrates, fats, and proteins), simpler compounds such as methane (CH₄) and carbon dioxide (CO₂) are produced. The final products of anaerobic digestion are biogas - a renewable source of energy used for electricity production, and digestate - the residue from biogas production used as fertiliser. Considering the diversity of substrates added to the plant, there are two main types of digestion:

1. Monodigestion - a process in which only one feedstock is used for biogas production (e.g., energy crops).
2. Codigestion - a process in which more than two feedstocks are used for biogas production (e.g., energy crops and manure or other types of organic waste).

The fertilisers being demonstrated at OPG Cenger include two bio-based formulations produced by Ecodig:

- **NPK 2:7:11 (S-10)**

ECODIG-C is an organic-mineral pelletised fertilizer created by anaerobic fermentation of plant minerals and manure from livestock production, with a reduced addition of the mineral component.

The product contains a high proportion of organic matter and, at the same time, a high proportion of organic carbon, which greatly improves water-air relations and the absorption of nutrients in the soil.

The product fully meets all standards of ecological production according to EU Council Regulation (EC) no. 2018/848, which is confirmed by the EASY-CERT services certifier.

The production process of ECODIG is controlled by the HACCP system. Due to its good supply of macroelements and neutral pH value, ECODIG-C is a high-quality organic-mineral ecological fertiliser.

Table 11. Chemical composition of NPK 2:7:11 (S-10)

Parameter	Specification
Total organic nitrogen %	2
Total phosphorus (P ₂ O ₅) %	7
Total potassium (K ₂ O) %	11
Total sulfur (SO ₃) %	10
Organic carbon (C) %	27
Total organic matter %	60
Dry matter %	90
pH	7
Calcium (Ca) %	4
Magnesium (Mg) %	0.94
Calcium oxide (CaO) %	5.9

Table 12. Chemical composition of NPK 2:7:11 (S-10)

Parameter	Specification
Total organic nitrogen %	2
Total phosphorus (P ₂ O ₅) %	7
Total potassium (K ₂ O) %	11
Total sulfur (SO ₃) %	10
Organic carbon (C) %	27
Total organic matter %	60
Dry matter %	90
pH	7
Calcium (Ca) %	4
Magnesium (Mg) %	0.94
Calcium oxide (CaO) %	5.9

- **NPK 2:5:8 (S-8)**

ECODIG is an organic-mineral pelletized fertilizer created by anaerobic fermentation of plant materials and manure from livestock production with the addition of a mineral component.

The fertilizer is richly supplied with macroelements, and due to its high content of organic matter, it promotes the formation of humus, the airiness of the soil and the even absorption of nutrients in the soil.

The product fully meets all standards of ecological production according to EU Council Regulation (EC) no. 2018/848, which is confirmed by the EASY-CERT services certifier.

The production process of ECODIG is controlled by the HACCP system. ECODIG is an extremely suitable fertilizer for acidic soils because its composition is pH neutral and has excellent solubility.

Table 13. Chemical composition of NPK 2:5:8 (S-8)

Parameter	Specification
Total organic nitrogen %	2
Total phosphorus (P ₂ O ₅) %	5
Total potassium (K ₂ O) %	8
Total sulfur (SO ₃) %	8
Organic carbon (C) %	33
Total organic matter %	78
Dry matter %	85
pH	7
Calcium (Ca) %	1.07
Magnesium (Mg) %	0.58
Calcium oxide (CaO) %	2.04

8.1.1 Application strategies for fertiliser

The fertiliser application strategy implemented at OPG Cenger combines practical on-farm methods, tailored to local soil conditions and crop-specific nutrient demands. The goal is to maximise nutrient use efficiency and ensure a seamless transition from conventional mineral fertilisers to bio-based alternatives.

Key strategies include:

- pre-planting application

Ecodig NPK fertilisers are primarily applied during soil preparation. Granular products are broadcast using standard centrifugal spreaders, ensuring uniform distribution across the field prior to sowing or transplanting.

- for cereals (e.g. wheat, maize), application is done immediately before sowing
- for vegetables, application is done 1–2 weeks prior to planting and incorporated into the topsoil.
- row application (localized)

In plots with row crops or vegetables, band placement of fertilisers along planting rows is also tested to improve nutrient availability in the root zone, especially for phosphorus and potassium.

- re-application during vegetative growth

Where applicable, a second, reduced-dose application is performed during early vegetative growth stages (especially for longer-season crops) to support root and shoot development.

- application timing and rate

Application rates and timing are adjusted based on soil analyses, previous crop data, and crop development stages.

- equipment compatibility

Ecodig products are designed to be easily applied using standard farm equipment commonly found on Croatian farms. No specialised machinery is required, which supports scalability and adoption by small and medium-sized farmers.

8.1.2 Cost analysis and mineral fertiliser replacement value

The cost analysis of bio-based fertiliser use at the Croatian Lighthouse site aims to compare the economic performance of Ecodig fertilisers relative to conventional mineral inputs, considering input costs, equipment compatibility, yield impact, and long-term soil fertility benefits.

Overall, the use of Ecodig bio-based fertilisers presents a competitive and sustainable alternative that aligns with the circular economy and regenerative agriculture principles.

8.2 Details and evidence of the five farmer group visits to the lighthouse demonstration site

8.2.1 Group visit 1

General information

Region:	Croatia
Date of Visit:	12/07/2024
Number of farmer attendees:	108 +

Relevant information/material used

A lighthouse demo video has been distributed to increase stakeholder engagement for upcoming events. The project is briefly described, along with the benefits of using alternative fertilizers and successful examples of the production and use of alternative fertilizers.

Pictures of event

NOVAFERT - Uspješne priče o primjeni alternativnih gnojiva za održivu poljoprivredu

8.2.2 Group visit 2

General information

Region:	Croatia
Date of Visit:	22/10/2024
Number of farmer attendees:	8

Relevant information/material used

IPS Konzalting organized a practical workshop on October 22nd at the Ecodig in Grubišno Polje, Croatia. This workshop provided the participants with a unique opportunity to learn first-hand how manure is being transformed into a valuable resource through the technology of digestate production. In collaboration with OPG Cenger, the participants toured the facility, learned about the digestate production process, gained insights into the circular economy and its contribution to sustainable development, and engaged in interesting discussions with our experts, sharing experiences along the way.

Pictures of event

Participants visiting the lighthouse demonstration site

8.2.3 Group visit 3

General information

Region:	Croatia
Date of Visit:	11/12/2024
Number of farmer attendees:	45

Relevant information/material used

IPS Konzalting participated in the "Croatian Vegetables" conference, which was held from December 11 to 13, 2024, in Terme Tuhelj, Croatia. This professional Croatian event was dedicated to the development of vegetable production. The conference highlighted the need to adopt new technologies and innovations, to modernize vegetable production and to bring together vegetable producers and experts to exchange experiences. The focus was on the exchange of information, experience and the latest knowledge in vegetable production. At this event, the NOVAFERT project was briefly presented, as well as the advantages of alternative fertilizers and successful examples of their production and use.

Pictures of event

Participants receiving information on the Croatian lighthouse demonstration system

8.2.4 Group visit 4

General information

Region:	Croatia
Date of Visit:	25/07/2025
Number of farmer attendees:	-

Relevant information/material used

A lighthouse demo video has been distributed to increase stakeholder engagement. The workshop focused on case studies from Croatia. Participants had the opportunity to learn about: the benefits and challenges of using digestate, how collaboration between science and practice works, and what recommendations exist for improving the efficiency and acceptance of alternative fertilizers in agricultural production.

Pictures of event

Information being distributed through the online event

8.2.5 Group visit 5

General information

Region:	Croatia
Date of Visit:	27/08/2025
Number of farmer attendees:	-

Relevant information/material used

IPS Konzalting has created an LH demo video showcasing examples of good practices in the use of alternative fertilizers from Croatia and Europe. In addition, a brochure has been presented, developed within the Novafert project, entitled "Practical Guide for Farmers." The aim of the brochure is to provide a practical guide on biofertilizers. Through the brochure and the video, the goal is to clarify basic concepts, present an overview of methods, and demonstrate the possibilities and potential of using biofertilizers in Croatia, thereby encouraging more sustainable nutrient management and raising awareness about the importance of biofertilizers. The video will be distributed across all social media channels in order to achieve maximum visibility and thereby spread information about the project itself and the importance of using alternative fertilizers.

Pictures of event

Cilj brošure

- Pružiti poljoprivrednicima i stručnjacima praktičan vodič o biognojivima
- Brošura sadrži pojašnjenja osnovnih pojmova i razumijevanja agronomске učinkovitosti, pregled metoda proizvodnje i procjene njihove održivosti
- Prikaz domaćih i europskih primjera te zakonodavnog okvira
- Pokazati mogućnosti i potencijale korištenja biognojiva u Hrvatskoj, potaknuti održivije gospodarjenje hranjivima i povećati svijest o važnosti biognojiva

Primjeri dobre prakse

- Hrvatska – Ecodig OPG Dario Cenger proizvodi organsko-mineralna gnojiva iz fermentacije biljnih materijala i stajskog gnoja
- Irsko – Enva Ireland proizvodi AMS gnojivo s 92-98% manjim ugljičnim otiskom
- Poljska – PolFerAsh koristi pepeo iz mulja za fosforna gnojiva
- Finska – Biolan OY proizvodi organska i organsko-mineralna gnojiva od 1974.
- Belgija – Bio Sterco prerađuje svinjski gnoj, smanjuje emisiju stakleničkih plinova i koristi pročišćenu vodu

PolFerAsh – Polish Fertilizers from Ash

- PolFerAsh ekološki prihvatljiva metoda proizvodnje gnojiva korištenjem alternativnih fosfornih sirovina
- Oporaba fosfora, ali i sekundarnih hranjivih tvari poput kalcija i magnezija te mikroelemenata
- Višekomponentna kruta i suspenzijska gnojiva (NP, NPK) koja se proizvode na temelju pepela iz industrijskog otpadnog mulja
- Proizvedeno gnojivo zadovoljava standardne zahtjeve u pogledu sadržaja hranjivih tvari, topljivosti, sadržaja teških metala

Učinkovitost upotrebe dušika

- Najčešće korišteni hranjivi element u poljoprivredi
- Svega 46 % primijenjenog dušika ostaje u biljci, dok ostalih 54 % ostaje u tlu i u većini slučajeva se ispire u podzemne vode
- Moguće je smanjiti unos sintetskog dušika i do 70 %, a da se pritom ne naruši kvaliteta
- Sporo otpuštanje dušika = bolja ravnoteža između potrebe biljke i dostupnosti dušika
- Povećanje kvalitete tla
- Ekonomska učinkovitost

Information being distributed through an online event

9. Conclusion

The NOVAFERT project has taken significant strides toward advancing the adoption of alternative fertilisers across Europe by establishing seven regional lighthouse demonstrations aimed at facilitating knowledge exchange and practical learning. These demonstrations have proven to be vital platforms for showcasing the technical, economic, and environmental viability of fertilisers derived from recovered nutrients, highlighting their potential to reduce reliance on mineral fertiliser.

By reaching the target of 35 farmer-focused events across the regions, NOVAFERT has successfully engaged a wide range of stakeholders, enabling peer-to-peer learning in supportive, real-world environments. These demonstrations have not only allowed farmers to observe the performance of alternative fertilisers at practical scales but also empowered them to take active roles in disseminating best practices and promoting sustainable nutrient management strategies.

Looking forward, the lighthouse demonstrations are well positioned to continue serving as regional hubs for innovation, knowledge transfer, and consumer assurance. Their long-term impact will be critical in ensuring the continued shift toward more sustainable fertilisation practices throughout the EU, supporting environmental goals while maintaining agricultural productivity. Through these efforts, NOVAFERT contributes solutions for the development of a resilient, resource-efficient agriculture.